

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF ORGANICALLY MODIFIED LAYERED ZINC PHENYLPHOSPHONATE/POLY(1,4-BUTYLENE CARBONATE-CO-TEREPHTHALATE)S NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the biocompatible organic dodecylamine and octadecylamine were selected to modify layered zinc phenylphosphonates (PPZns) (designated as C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn). C₁₂-PPZn and C₁₈-PPZn were added into the poly(butylene carbonate-co-terephthalate) (PBCT) polymer matrix as nucleating agents. The results of wide angle x-ray diffraction (WAXD) and transmission electron microscope (TEM) demonstrate that PPZn layers were intercalated by PBCT polymer chains. The crystallization properties of nanocomposites were analyzed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Experimental results of non-isothermal and isothermal melt crystallization kinetics showed that PPZn had a significant impact on crystallization behavior of PBCT. With the presence of organic modified-PPZn, the T_c of PBCT increases significantly. Upon the addition of 5% C₁₂-PPZn, the crystallization half-times at 125 °C of the PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn composite decrease from 7.68 min of pure PBCT to 2.09 min of 5 wt% nanocomposites.

Experiment

Fig 1: Schematic diagram of adding octadecylamine intercalated PPZn to a PBCT matrix to form nanocomposites.

Characterization results

Fig 2: WAXD patterns for (a) PPZn, C₁₂-PPZn, PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn and (b) PPZn, C₁₈-PPZn, PBCT/C₁₈-PPZn nanocomposites.

Fig 4: DSC curves of non-isothermal melt crystallization and for PBCT/modified-PPZn nanocomposites.

Fig 3: TEM micrographs for (a) 5wt% PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn and (b) 5wt% PBCT/C₁₈-PPZn nanocomposites.

Isothermal crystallization results

Fig 5: The relative crystallinity (X_c) as a function of the crystallization time (t) for PBCT and PBCT/modified-PPZn nanocomposites melt-crystallized. (a) pure PBCT, (b) 1wt% C₁₂-PPZn, (c) 3wt% C₁₂-PPZn, (d) 5wt% C₁₂-PPZn, (e) 1wt% C₁₈-PPZn, (f) 3wt% C₁₂-PPZn, (g) 5wt% C₁₂-PPZn.

Fig 6: The representative Avrami plots of PBCT and PBCT/modified-PPZn nanocomposites at different T_c for (a) pure PBCT, (b) 1wt% C₁₂-PPZn, (c) 3wt% C₁₂-PPZn, (d) 5wt% C₁₂-PPZn, (e) 1wt% C₁₈-PPZn, (f) 3wt% C₁₂-PPZn (g) 5wt% C₁₂-PPZn.

Fig 7: Dependence of the crystallization half time on T_c for the (a) PBCT/C₁₂-PPZn and (b) PBCT/C₁₈-PPZn nanocomposites.